

INSTADINE

Version 0

Description

Institutionalization of attention to student diversity and inclusion in higher education: Diverse students' voices

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

USAL4EXCELLENCE

Researchers

Maria Cruz Sanchez Gomez, Hemendra Mistry

Organizations

Universidad de Salamanca

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [INSTADINE](#)

Description:

Institutionalization of attention to student diversity and inclusion in higher education: Diverse students' voices

Researchers:

[Maria Cruz Sanchez Gomez](#)

[Hemendra Mistry](#)

Organizations:

[Universidad de Salamanca](#)

Contact: [Hemendra Mistry](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)||[EC](#)

Grants: [USAL4EXCELLENCE](#)

Project: [INSTADINE](#)

3. License

License: [AFL-3.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

INSTADINE

The study falls into three broad objectives, viz., 1) to identify strategies for paying attention to student diversity and inclusion in higher education; 2) to develop and validate the INSTADINE scale; and 3) to determine diverse student perceptions of university practices on student diversity and inclusion in higher education, covered under the seven work packages (WPs).

The following work packages are associated with data generation:

WP1: To identify university strategies for paying attention to student diversity and inclusion in higher education.

This phase involved an online survey of universities in four European countries (France, Spain, Sweden, and the UK), which was associated with survey data. We collected quantitative data in the online survey using the Qualtrics tool. The main purpose of this phase was to collect data on the universities' strategies, policies, and practices for student diversity and inclusion in higher education. We provided the universities with an e-rubric consisting of a variety of close-ended items related to their strategies and practices on student diversity and inclusion in higher education. The universities had to select the appropriate answer(s) from the options given with each item. The university authorities' responses generated the survey data.

WP2: To develop and validate the INSTADINE scale to assess students' perceptions of attention to diversity and inclusion in higher education.

This phase's data generation has the goal of involving students from diverse backgrounds in the exploration of their perceptions of diversity and inclusion practices in universities. Therefore, this phase involves an online survey of students from diverse backgrounds, which encourages them to reflect on their university's policies and practices related to student diversity and inclusion in higher education.

WP2 will also include pilot testing of a draft scale and data analysis, including psychometric analysis by the PI, with the goal of developing a reliable and valid scale.

WP3: To determine students' perceptions with regard to demographic variables.

This phase entails a variable-wise analysis of the data (gender, age, level of education, type of diverse category, and disability), reflecting how the diverse students perceive the university's practices in fostering diversity and inclusion in higher education. The results of this data will assist universities in understanding the extent to which they are meeting the diverse needs of students in higher education, the progress and growth they have made in addressing student diversity and inclusion, and the areas that still need further attention. Contributing to higher educational development in general and policy dialogues in particular, the results will provide valuable insights on how the students perceive university practices on diversity and inclusion in higher education, help in developing new policies and practices for attending to student diversity, and contribute to effective inclusive higher education for all.

WP4: Utilize the findings from WP1 to WP3, and ensure the dissemination and communication of the results.

After collecting and analysing the data is complete, WP4 involves the creation of a rubric for the universities and a perception scale for students with diverse backgrounds in higher education. Conference presentations, journal publications, and secondments at a collaborating research centre and a non-academic organization will facilitate this phase, which draws on pseudonymized and anonymized data to generate Open Access publications and presentations. We will make both the developed instruments (rubric and perception scale) and all the research-generated publications available in an Open Access repository at USAL.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

No, I will not reuse any existing "raw" data from other repositories.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

We will collect primary data through the anonymous survey of the universities and students with diverse backgrounds. Pseudonymization will be used to save the collected data on a local hard disk, accessible only to the principal investigator.

1.1.5 What is its format?

This project generated anonymous survey data from 32 universities (in France, Spain, Sweden, and the UK) through the e-rubric and stored it in digital formats (.xlsx and .pdf).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

4-5 mb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

The data from the universities and diverse students are required to know the status of attention to students with diverse backgrounds in higher education, and diverse students perceptions of attention to their diversities and inclusion in higher education so as to assess the practices on student diversity and inclusion policies, as well as the areas that require further attention.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The Qualtrics survey tool administered an e-rubric to 32 participating universities to collect the survey data. We will also generate additional survey data from a diverse student population.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

- Decision makers
- Education

The data will be useful to the stakeholders and policymakers involved in the practices and policies related to student diversity and inclusion in higher education. The data will also be useful to higher education institutions in assessing their practices on student diversity and inclusion policies, as well as the areas that require further attention.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Permanent ID and DOI (digital object identifier) number will be assigned to each data file deposited in Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

A rich metadata to facilitate the discovery of rubrics and diverse student survey data will be provided adhering to the DDI standards to enhance data discoverability.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Statistical

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

The metadata can be found on zenodo.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

We will save the data collected through university surveys in a combined file named YYYYMMDD_RUB_SURVEY. We will adhere to the naming conventions of YYYYMMDD_RUB_CONT for country-wise data and YYYYMMDD_RUB_Pseudonym for individual university-wise data, or 01, 02, and so on, if required. We will adhere to a similar naming convention for the combined data collected from students with diverse backgrounds. For example, YYYYMMDD_INSTA_SURVEY. Use YYYYMMDD_INSTA_SWDB for the diverse group-wise data, or 01, 02, etc., if necessary.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

OpenAPC Global Initiative

GREDOS, ZENODO

<https://gredos.usal.es/>

<https://zenodo.org>

The Document Repository Management System of the University of Salamanca (GREDOS) offers online consultation of digital documents with

historical, scientific, educational and institutional content. The University of Salamanca disseminates heritage collections, scientific documents and educational and information resources in open access through GREDOS.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Supports retention
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Accounts have been created on GREDOS and ZENODO repositories, and the data files will be deposited after the coding and cleaning of the data. The publications of the results will also be made open access through USAL repository (GREDOS).

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

20240902_INSTADINE_Rubric

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

on zenodo.org

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The data are anonymous, and no person or institute can be identified.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The data will be available until 2 years of project completion in 2025. There is no embargo.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

The detailed information is available in Data Management Plan.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Please see above

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Yes

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

We will save the data collected through university surveys in a combined file named YYYYMMDD_RUB_SURVEY. We will adhere to the naming conventions of YYYYMMDD_RUB_CONT for country-wise data and YYYYMMDD_RUB_Pseudonym for individual university-wise data, or 01, 02, and so on, if required. We will adhere to a similar naming convention for the combined data collected from students with diverse backgrounds. For example, YYYYMMDD_INSTA_SURVEY. Use YYYYMMDD_INSTA_SWDB for the diverse group-wise data, or 01, 02, etc., if necessary.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Please see 3.3.5 above

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Use of tools for automatic checks

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

1500

Euro

- Storage
- Security

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of national infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Hemendra Mistry (orcid:0000-0002-9074-0111)
- b. Maria Cruz Sanchez Gomez

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

PI

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

The data sets can be accessed through the institutional ID and password.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access

- Data storage

USAL Research will also store all data in OneDrive. The PI and the ICT department of USAL will securely store the passwords for encryption management, and they will also encrypt the folders on the PI's desktop and server. As soon as the computer connects to the internet and the VPN, USAL's secure server automatically backs up all files on the PI's desktop.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Salamanca University's research repository (GREDOS) ensures long-term data and metadata preservation. The project will end after 30 months, destroying the original data and retaining only the anonymized data in the two repositories (GREDOS and Zenodo).

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

The surveys do not ask for personal information, except for university names. The USAL Research Ethics Committee has approved the project, and it adheres to the Helsinki Recommendations. Therefore, no sensitive data will be shared when it becomes publicly available.

https://usalinvestigacion.eu.qualtrics.com/CP/File.php?F=F_00Oes736ojDwQ5M

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

Yes

The consent forms for all participants include a simple description of the study and the data treatment.

Anonymized data will be used for the analysis, presentation at conferences and publication of the results. Only pseudonymized data will be available via open-access repositories (OpenAIRE, GREDOS, and Zenodo). Small selections of anonymized data may be presented at European Open Day events and public venues, such as USAL's website, blog, or social media accounts.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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